

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Object;

Alya Paper Analysis For ***THE MEANING OF FAMILY LOVE IN FAMILY FILM***

Background and Analysis

The film is one of the visual communication media in the form of moving images based on a story or script that has been designed. In choosing a film, most people choose a film that can take them into the plot of the film, make them feel everything that is done by the characters and events in the film so that they get carried away. The Cemara family began to be updated in a more modern and millennial version in 2019 and made into a cinema or feature film. This study aims to describe the meaning of family love in the film Keluarga Cemara. This research is also expected to be useful in analyzing the meaning of the storyline of a film using qualitative analysis methods. The research method used in this research is the descriptive analysis research method with a qualitative approach. The qualitative research method is one type of research used to examine human and social problems. The results of this study indicate that the meaning of family affection in the film Keluarga Cemara is interpreted by the many sacrifices of a father, communication between families, and the harmonious atmosphere described by the storyline.

From the results of this study, it can be concluded that the meaning and moral message in this film that can be taken and interpreted, is that a family will depend on and give to each other to make each other happy, besides that the meaning of the sacrifice of a father or parent is so great. , where parents always try to give their best for a decent life and make a child happy.

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Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions:

1.) Is it Available data or information to answer it,

Yes, here is some data and information available with qualitative data collection techniques

2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

Yes, the data obtained was obtained through direct observation, by watching a film, the data will be taken for this journal

3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),

Yes, this research meets the requirements of originality and identification

4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,

No, because this is just an expression of my heart and the inspiration that comes to my mind

5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,

Yes, I took an incident that relates to a family environment

6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and

No, this journal only requires observation by watching the film, it doesn't have to involve the wider community

7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

No, the problems contained in this journal are not limited by the interests of the author

8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

Just seeing from something that usually happens in the family environment

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

Can embrace family members more and realize more that family love is something precious

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REFERENCES

Kress, Gunther, and Theo Van Leeuwen. *Reading images: The grammar of visual design*. Routledge, 2020.

Morgan, Jacob. *The future of work: Attract new talent, build better leaders, and create a competitive organization*. John Wiley & Sons, 2014.

Nurhasanah, E., Maspuroh, U., Nordin, M. N., & Jalil, A. G. Study Of Dialogue As A Character Education Media In The Film "Keluarga Cemara", 2019

Li, Nannan. "4 The development of the European film industry between 2017 and 2018." *Development of the Global Film Industry* (2020): 50.

Côté-Arsenault, Denise, and Erin Denney-Koelsch. "'Have no regrets:' Parents' experiences and developmental tasks in pregnancy with a lethal fetal diagnosis." *Social science & medicine* 154 (2016): 100-109.

Okai, Andrew Nii Okai. "Movies That Sell: Rhetorical Analysis of Product Placements in Marvel Movies." (2021). Flick, Uwe. Routledge, 2016

Prawira, Nanang Ganda. "Understanding the motif meaning of dermayon batik as women's expression." *TAWARIKH* 6.1 (2014).